

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Assessment readiness template

Full resource

Table of contents

Introduction	2
Summary.....	2
Assessment readiness template	3
Instructions for filling in the template.....	3
Your commitments	4
Goals of assessment process.....	7
Context of assessment process.....	7
Resources and expertise available	7
Data sources	8
Assessment methods	8
Documentation and evaluating the evaluation	8
References	9

Introduction

Summary

This template helps organizations reflect on their maturity level in responsible research assessment (RRA) reform by guiding them through targeted questions. It also supports internal discussions, planning, and the monitoring of ongoing research assessment (RA) progress.

The section on assessment readiness focuses on organizational commitments, including policies and alignment with initiatives such as CoARA, ARRA, the DORA Declaration, the Leiden Manifesto, and the Barcelona Declaration. Goals of RA can, for example, be compared with the European Commission’s 2019 report. The template addresses also practical aspects, with questions on available resources and expertise, data sources used, assessment methods, and documentation of the RA process.

Overcoming common obstacles in implementing RRA is discussed in the Guide for overcoming common obstacles in implementing RRA <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526054>.

Template as part of SCOPE+i Resources and in relation to SCOPE Framework

The [SCOPE+i Resources](#) aims to facilitate the transition towards Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) with particular focus on contributions to OS. Being one out of 17 resources (guides, templates and checklists), this template supports the structured organization of research assessment process and information from initial planning through to the publication of assessment protocols.

[SCOPE Framework](#) is a five-stage model for evaluating responsibly. It is a practical step-by-step process designed to help research managers, or anyone involved in conducting research evaluations, in planning new evaluations as well as checking existing evaluations. SCOPE is an acronym, where S stands for START with what you value, C for CONTEXT considerations, O for OPTIONS for evaluating, P for PROBE deeply, and E for EVALUATE your evaluation. This guide is most relevant for stages S and C.

Figure 1. SCOPE Framework by INORMS (2023) (modified by highlighting the most relevant stages for this resource).

More about SCOPE Framework in International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

All SCOPE+i Resources are brought together in the [GraspOS Infrastructure](#) (i), a simple, user-friendly interface (UI) where you can explore project results and save documents to learn and share with others.

Assessment readiness template

Instructions for filling in the template

Answer the following questions describing your readiness to carry out a responsible research assessment (RRA) process. It is recommended to fill in the form in cooperation with all who are responsible for the practical implementation of the assessment process e.g. administration, human resources and library.

Explore also the [Toolkit for recognizing and rewarding open research](#) published by the University of Bristol with [Open and Responsible Researcher Reward and Recognition Project](#) (OR4) in 2024. The toolkit is designed to help universities and other research-performing organisations implement effective recognition and reward for open research through researcher assessment practices. The two components of the toolkit are:

1. [maturity framework and self-assessment tool](#) that institutions can use to assess their maturity in the implementation of relevant policies and procedures, to support internal discussion and planning, and to measure ongoing progress
2. [implementation guide](#) consisting of an introduction and sections linked to corresponding action areas in the maturity framework, providing detailed practical guidance to support assessment, planning and progress

Table: Action areas of the Recognising and rewarding open research toolkit - [Toolkit overview](#)

Strategy and leadership	1. Institutional commitment 2. Leadership 3. Strategy and planning
Implementation	4. Communication and engagement 5. Policy and procedure 6. Support, systems and processes 7. Guidance and training
Managing progress	8. Monitoring and evaluation 9. Research planning

(UK Reproducibility Network, 2024)

Your commitments

Organizational policies

Has your organization published policies, principles and guidelines for RA and OS? Add the name of the policy papers and date of publications with links below.

On what international and national declarations are your organizational principles and guidelines based on? Put ticks in relevant boxes.

Declaration or initiative	Yes	No
CoARA		
ARRA		
DORA		
Leiden Manifesto		

Barcelona Declaration		
Other(s)		

How do your organizational policies and principles affect your OS aware RA processes?

CoARA

Are you a member of [CoARA](#)? Have you signed the [ARRA](#) agreement? Date of signatory? Do you have a CoARA action plan? Please add also the reference to your CoARA action plan with PID.

What does CoARA membership and ARRA signatory mean to you in practice? According to your CoARA action plan, what are the practical steps to change the RRA processes in a more responsible direction, taking into account OS?

DORA

Have you signed the [DORA Declaration](#)? Date of signatory?

What practices and methods do you use in evaluation of the quality of research outputs? What kind of metrics and indicators do you use? What is the role of qualitative evaluation?

Leiden Manifesto

Are you familiar with the [Leiden Manifesto](#)? How are the ten [principles](#) taken into account in your assessment process?

Barcelona Declaration

Have you signed the [Barcelona Declaration](#)? Date of signatory?

In your organization, how openness of research information is implemented in using and producing research? What is the openness level of your research information systems and services? How is the Barcelona Declaration applied in OS aware RRA?

Goals of assessment process

Are you familiar with the goals of evaluation defined e.g. by the [European Commission](#) (2019)? What are the goals of your assessment process?

Context of assessment process

Describe the specifics of your assessment process in as diverse a manner as possible. For example: How does the size of the entity and discipline affect?

Context of assessment process is discussed more in:

- Purpose and context statement template <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525469>
- Indicators Guide 2: Frameworks and toolboxes for open research <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17181862>
- Guide on choosing an assessment method <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525721>

Resources and expertise available

Who and what departments (functions) in your organizations are involved with the assessment process? Level of expertise of OS and responsible RA?

Explore the Guide for assembling an assessment team <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525548> which discusses diverse perspectives, expertises and experiences that are important to consider when compiling an assessment team, i.e. group of experts, for a RA process.

Data sources

What information sources are used? Describe the data the assessment process is based on? Quality of data? Availability of data? Openness of data Verification of data?

Explore Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526168> which discusses non-commercial databases OpenAlex, OpenAIRE, BIP!Services and OpenCitations.

Assessment methods

What assessment methods are used? What metrics and indicators are used?

Explore Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526168> which discusses e.g. about use of metrics in RA.

Documentation and evaluating the evaluation

How are different stages of the assessment process documented? How is the evaluating of the evaluation carried out?

Explore the Checklist for responsible assessment <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15524455>

References

European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Schomberg, R., Britt Holbrook, J., Oancea, A., Kamerlin, S. et al., Indicator frameworks for fostering open knowledge practices in science and scholarship, Publications Office, 2019, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/445286>

International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

UK Reproducibility Network. 2024. Recognising and rewarding open research. <https://recognition.ukrn-openresearch.ac.uk/>

